

Studies on Hydrofluorene Derivatives. Part II. Synthesis of 1,1a,1b,2,3,4,4a,5,6,6a-Decahydro-1a-methyl-3-oxochrysofluorene

Bidyut Kamal Bhattacharyya, Ashoke Kumar Bose, Amareshwar Chatterjee,
and (Late) Beda Prasad Sen

The synthesis of a pure isomer of 1,1a,1b,2,3,4,4a,5,6,6a-decahydro-1a-methyl-3-oxochrysofluorene (XV) has been achieved through the steps:

(I: R=H; R₁=Me) → (II) → (III: R=R₁=Me) → (V) → (VI) → (XI) → (XV) and (III: R=R₁=Me) → (IV: R=R₁=H) → (VIII: R=R₁=H) → (IX) → (VIII: R=CH₂.CH₂.CO₂H; R₁=H) → (X) → (VIII: R=CH₂.CH₂.COMe; R₁=H) → (XIV) → (XV).

In continuation of our work¹, the synthesis² of 1,1a,1b,2,3,4,4a,5,6,6a-decahydro-1a-methyl-3-oxochrysofluorene is described below.

Diethyl 1-keto-2-indanylmethylmalonate (I: R=CO₂Et; R₁=Et), prepared by methylation of diethyl 1-keto-2-indanylmalonate³, was hydrolysed and decarboxylated with mineral acid to furnish crystalline 2-1'-carboxyethyl-1-oxoindane (I: R=R₁=H). Its methyl ester (I: R=H; R₁=Me), when subjected to the Stobbe condensation with dimethyl succinate in presence of potassium *t*-butoxide according to the condition of Johnson *et al.*⁴, yielded a half-ester, which on esterification afforded the unsaturated trimethyl ester (II), λ_{max} 272 mμ (ε, 12590), as an oil. The yield of this condensation was considerably increased with larger amounts of alkoxide, but the condensation product (II) showed λ_{max} 264-268 mμ (ε, 10450). A reasonable explanation of the UV absorption seems to be that the proportion of generated *cis*- and *trans*-cinnamic ester chromophores, present in (II), may be different with changed concentration of alkoxide.

The hydrolysis and subsequent decarboxylation⁴ of the unsaturated trimethyl ester (II) was performed with acid. The resulting crude acidic material was converted with methanolic sulphuric acid to the unsaturated dimethyl ester (III: R=R₁=Me), λ_{max} 258 mμ (ε, 12590). But the esterification with diazomethane resulted in the formation of a neutral product, which showed λ_{max} 259 mμ (ε, 7413), indicating it to be a mixture comprising 60% of the above dimethyl ester (III: R=R₁=Me) and 40% of a lactonic methyl ester (*vide infra*).

The pure ester (III: R=R₁=Me) afforded on saponification the crystalline acid (III: R=R₁=H), λ_{max} 262 mμ (ε, 12500). The ester and the acid (III) might have ethylenic linkage conjugated with benzene nucleus either in the exocyclic or in the endocyclic position. The endocyclic structure (III) is preferred from analogy to the observation

1. Sen *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1958, 35, 751.

2. Bhattacharyya *et al.*, *Science & Culture*, 1959, 24, 533; 1961, 27, 152; 1962, 28, 337.

3. Groves and Swan, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 867.

4. Johnson *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 3395.

of Cleme *et al.*⁵, who prepared an endocyclic monobasic acid by the same sequence of reactions starting from indan-1-one. Further, this structure is also preferred if the conclusions of Turner and Garner⁶, who examined the stability differences in a number of isomer-pairs possessing exocyclic and endocyclic double bonds, are taken into consideration. The comparison of absorption maxima of these compounds (III: $R=R_1=Me$ and $R=R_1=H$) with those of 2,3-dimethylindene⁷ and 1,2,3,4-tetrahydrofluorene⁷ (λ_{max} 258 μ ; ϵ , 10720 and 260 μ ; ϵ , 13180, respectively) also support the endocyclic structure (III).

(I)

(II)

(III)

(IV)

(V)

(VI)

(VII)

(VIII)

(IX)

The unsaturated dimethyl ester (III: $R=R_1=Me$) having higher extinction coefficient afforded on catalytic hydrogenation the saturated dimethyl ester (IV: $R=R_1=Me$) in quantitative yield. The same treatment of the aforementioned neutral product having lower extinction coefficient furnished the same saturated ester (IV: $R=R_1=Me$) together with a crystalline half-ester (IV: $R=H$; $R_1=Me$). The smooth hydrogenolysis of the lactone clearly points to the presence of a benzyl—oxygen bond in the molecule. Similar hydrogenolysis has been recorded by Groves and Swan⁸.

5. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 863.6. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 80, 1424.7. Christol *et al.*, *Compt. rend.*, 1956, 243, 1532; *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1958, 248.

The above saturated dimethyl ester afforded on saponification a mixture of isomeric acids (IV: R=R₁ =H) from which two products, A (m.p. 168-68.5°) and B (m.p. 147.5°), were isolated, the former being preponderant. The half-ester (IV: R=H; R₁=Me) furnished on similar treatment the lower melting acid B only. The equilibration of pure dimethyl esters of these two acids with sodium methoxide, according to the procedure of Sorkin and Reichstein⁸, clearly proves that these differ in stereochemistry at the carbon atom marked with an asterisk in (IV). Although optically active 2-phenylbutane has been racemised⁹ with potassium *t*-butoxide in *t*-butanol, yet the possibility of epimerisation at benzyl position 1 of (IV) may safely be excluded here for the milder condition of experimentation. The dimethyl ester (IV: R=R₁ =Me), prepared from the acid B (IV: R=R₁ =H), yielded on partial saponification, according to the condition of Dawson and Ramage¹⁰, a new half-ester (IV: R=Me; R₁=H).

The Dieckmann cyclisation of the unsaturated dimethyl ester (III: R=R₁ = Me) afforded a homogeneous unsaturated β -keto-ester (V). The placing of the double bond in (V) is based on the generalisation of Ingold¹¹. The unsaturated β -keto-ester (V) was converted by catalytic hydrogenation to the saturated compound (VIII: R=H; R₁=CO₂Me) from which a pure crystalline component was isolated.

The ester (V) was hydrolysed and decarboxylated under controlled acidic condition to furnish a mixture of ketones (double bond isomers) from which was isolated a pure component (VI) in 10% yield. The conjugation of the double bond with the carbonyl group in (VI) is in agreement with its UV and IR spectra.

The ester (V) afforded on treatment with 6*N*-HCl and glacial acetic acid 1-methylfluorene. It is known that 6 α - and 6 β -hydroxy- Δ^4 -cholestene-3-ones are isomerised¹² in presence of acid to cholestane-3,6-dione. If the reverse of this transformation is assumed to occur in the present case, the following intermediates may be postulated for the elimination of oxygen from position 2 of (V).

Further, it was observed that ester (V) was smoothly aromatised with methanolic acid to (VII: R = CO₂Me). It can be safely concluded, based on the observation of

8. *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1946, 29, 1209.

9. Cram *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 83, 3686.

10. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 3382.

11. "Structure and Mechanism in Organic Chemistry", Cornell University Press, Ithaca, New York, 1953, p. 562.

12. Fieser, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 4377.

Hückel and Schewen¹³, that this aromatisation takes place through a dihydrofluorene derivative, *i.e.*, the enol of the unsaturated β -keto-ester (V). Similar phenomenon has been observed by Howell and Taylor¹⁴.

The ester (VII: R=CO₂Me) was saponified to the acid (VII: R=CO₂H), which on decarboxylation afforded the phenol (VII: R=H). The latter compound was also obtained by dehydrogenation of the unsaturated ketone (VI), m.p. 115-20°.

Pyrolysis of the dibasic acids (IV: R=R₁=H), A and B, the Dieckmann cyclisation of the corresponding dimethyl esters (IV: R=R₁=Me), followed by treatment with acid and hydrolysis and decarboxylation of the crystalline β -keto-ester (VIII: R=H; R₁=CO₂Me) afforded the same crystalline ketone (VIII: R=R₁=H) as the preponderant component.

The saturated compounds (IV), prepared by catalytic hydrogenation of the unsaturated compounds (III), are expected to possess *cis*-stereochemistry according to the concept of Linstead *et al.*¹⁵. Hence the ketone (VIII: R = R₁ = H) should have *cis*-ring juncture. House *et al.*¹⁶ have shown that the *cis*-isomer of 1,2,3,4,10,11-hexahydro-9-oxo-fluorene is more stable than the *trans*-isomer. In agreement with this, metal-ammonia reduction of the pure ketone (VI), which was expected¹⁷ to produce more stable product, afforded the ketone (VIII: R=R₁=H) as the major component.

Incidentally, if the rules postulated by Stork and Darling¹⁸ regarding the reduction of $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated ketone with lithium in ammonia is applicable in this system, the ring-juncture hydrogen atom β to the carbonyl group must be axial to the ketonic ring of the saturated ketone (VIII: R=R₁=H). Catalytic reduction of the pure ketone (VI) furnished a mixture of saturated ketones from which the crystalline ketone (VIII: R = R₁ = H) was also isolated as its 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone.

The unsaturated ketone (VI) was condensed with 1-diethylaminobutan-3-one according to the condition of Johnson *et al.*¹⁹ to afford the unsaturated ketone (XI). Evidence for the nuclear structure of the latter compound was provided by its reduction, followed by dehydrogenation to chrysofluorene, which was oxidised to 11-oxochrysofluorene.

The purpose of preparing the unsaturated ketone (XI) has been to convert it into all possible isomers of the completely saturated ketone (XV), modelling the experiments after those of Johnson's monumental work²⁰ on steroid. Unfortunately, the limited results obtained by us seem to be unpromising.

The UV spectra of the ketal (XII), $\lambda_{\max}$ 258-259 m μ (ϵ , 11810), prepared from the ketone (XI) with ethylene glycol in presence of *p*-toluenesulphonic acid, indicate that one of the double bonds is conjugated with the aromatic ring. The other double bond

13. *Ber.*, 1956, 89, 1956.

14. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 3011.

15. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 64, 1985.

16. *Ibid.*, 1960, 82, 1457; cf. Bailey *et al.*, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1963, No. 9, 555.

17. Barton and Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 3045.

18. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 82, 1512.

19. *Ibid.*, 1956, 78, 6285.

20. *Ibid.*, 1956, 78, 6278.

has been placed between C-4a and C-5 from analogy²⁰. Reduction of the ketal (XII) with lithium in liquid ammonia furnished two pure isomers of (XIII), m.p. 123° and 125-26°, in 11% and 10% yield, respectively. Deketalisation of each of these pure isomers afforded two pure $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated ketones (XIV). In view of the poor yield of the ketals (XIII), it seems undesirable to speculate about the stereochemistry of the ketones (XIV). Catalytic reduction of the lower melting ketone (XIV) furnished a mixture, from which no pure isomer could be isolated.

Catalytic reduction of the ketone (XI) afforded the saturated ketone (XV, m.p. 132-33°) in 14% yield, two moles of hydrogen having been absorbed without appreciable change in the rate. It is rather unexpected that a tetra-substituted conjugated double bond is reduced at a rate equal to that of an $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated ketone.

That the rings B and C of the saturated ketone (XV), m.p. 132-33°, are *cis*-fused is clearly indicated by its preparation from the ketone (VIII: R = R₁ = H), following the elegant method of Woodward *et al.*²¹.

The ketone (VIII: R = R₁ = H) was converted with ethyl formate into the formyl derivative (VIII: R = H; R₁ = CHO), which on treatment with monomethylaniline furnished the crystalline anilinomethylene compound (IX). The latter on treatment with acrylonitrile in presence of Triton B, followed by alkali, afforded the keto-acid (VIII: R = CH₂-CH₂-CO₂H; R₁ = H). The enol lactone (X), prepared from the keto-acid with acetic anhydride and potassium acetate, was converted with methylmagnesium iodide into the diketone (VIII: R = CH₂CH₂COMe; R₁ = H), which was cyclised with a base to an isomeric mixture of ketones, from which a crystalline mixture of (XIV) was isolated. This material on catalytic hydrogenation afforded a mixture, from which was isolated the same saturated ketone (XV), m.p. 132-33°.

In order to investigate the stereochemistry of the A/B ring junction, the crystalline ketone (XV) was brominated to afford a crystalline bromo compound, which with γ -collidine did not furnish any fruitful result.

21. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 4223.

*EXPERIMENTAL.

Diethyl 1-Keto-2-indanylmethylmalonate (I: R = CO₂Et; R₁ = Et).—The yield of diethyl 1-keto-2-indanylmalonate³ was increased to 70-75% according to the following condition.

To a suspension of diethyl sodiomalonate, prepared from sodium dust (5 g.), dry benzene (50 ml), absolute ethanol (3.8 ml), and diethyl malonate (64 g.), was added dropwise with shaking a solution of crude 2-bromoindan-1-one²² (35 g.) in dry benzene (35 ml). A slight rise in temperature was observed and the reaction mixture assumed a yellow colour, changing to dark brown when the addition was complete. It was refluxed for 10-12 hr. and worked up to afford the desired product.

To the almost homogeneous sodio enolate, prepared from sodium dust (1.5 g.), dry benzene (120 ml), and a solution of the above 1-keto-2-indanylmalonate (15 g.) in dry benzene (60 ml), was added methyl iodide (22 g.); the reaction mixture was refluxed for 5 hr. and then worked up to afford the desired product (13 g.), b.p. 160-62°/0.2 mm. (Found: C, 66.90; H, 6.54. C₁₇H₂₀O₅ requires C, 67.10; H, 6.62%). This product solidified on keeping in a frigidaire. A portion of this solid on repeated crystallisations from petroleum (b.p. 60-80°) afforded a colorless material, m.p. 64-65°. (Found: C, 66.76; H, 6.83. C₁₇H₂₀O₅ requires C, 67.10; H, 6.62%).

2-1'-Carboxyethyl-1-oxaindane (I: R = R₁ = H).—The preceding product (I: R = CO₂Et; R₁ = Et; 35 g.) was hydrolysed and decarboxylated by refluxing with a mixture of HCl (conc., 350 ml) and water (350 ml) for 25 hr. The reaction mixture was cooled in ice and the crystalline material was filtered (19 g.); m.p.* 108-110°. A portion of this acid was recrystallised repeatedly from methanol (dil.), m.p., 132-34°; λ_{max} 244 mμ (ε, 13500). (Found: C, 70.63; H, 6.27. C₁₂H₁₂O₃ requires C, 70.58; H, 5.94%).

The *semicarbazone* of the keto-acid was prepared with semicarbazide hydrochloride and sodium acetate in aqueous solution and crystallised four times from methanol, m.p. 190-91° (decomp.). (Found: C, 59.48; H, 5.82; N, 16.13. C₁₅H₁₅O₃N₃ requires C, 59.73; H, 5.79; N, 16.08%).

2-1'-Methoxycarbonylethyl-1-oxaindane (I: R = H; R₁ = Me).—The acid (16 g.) was refluxed with methanol (110 ml) and H₂SO₄ (conc., 10 ml) for 16 hr. to furnish the ester (15 g.); b.p. 135-40°/0.5 mm. (Found: C, 71.33; H, 6.59. C₁₃H₁₄O₃ requires C, 71.52; H, 6.47%).

1-1',2'-Bis-(methoxycarbonyl)ethylidene-2-1'-methoxycarbonylethylindane (II).—(a). The Stobbe condensation of the keto-ester (I: R = H; R₁ = Me), following the condition of Sen *et al.*¹, yielded a crude acid-ester, which on esterification with diazomethane, followed by short-path distillation, afforded the unsaturated trimethyl ester (II) in 43% yield; b.p. 155-60°/0.15 mm, λ_{max} 272 mμ (ε, 12590). (Found: C, 65.89; H, 6.53. C₁₉H₂₂O₆ requires C, 65.88; H, 6.39%).

*The absorption spectra were examined in 95% ethanol by the Unicam Spectrophotometer S.P. 500. 22. Johnson and Shelberg, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 1745.

†In subsequent experiments a material having the previously reported m.p. (*Science & Culture*, 1959, 24, 533) could not be obtained.

(b). To a stirred solution of potassium *t*-butoxide, prepared from potassium (8.2 g.) and *t*-butanol (160 ml), was added slowly under nitrogen dimethyl succinate (30 ml) during $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. To the resulting yellow homogeneous mixture was added during $1\frac{1}{2}$ hr. a solution of the keto-ester (7 g.) in *t*-butanol (6 ml). The reaction mixture assumed a deep red colour which changed to green and ultimately to dark brown. It was stirred for further 2-3 hr. and the reaction was allowed to proceed for 12-14 hr. more without stirring. On working up, the crude dark brown gummy acidic material (11 g.) was esterified by refluxing with a mixture of methanol (110 ml) and H_2SO_4 (conc., 7 ml) for 24 hr. The ester was worked up to furnish the trimethyl ester in 63% yield; b.p. 187-92°/0.4 mm, λ_{max} 264-268 μ (ϵ , 10450). (Found: C, 65.61; H, 6.75. $C_{19}H_{22}O_6$ requires C, 65.88; H, 6.39%).

(c). The yield was increased to 70-75% according to the following procedure. To the stirred keto-ester (23 g.), under nitrogen, was added during 3 hr. at the room temperature a pale yellow homogeneous mixture of potassium *t*-butoxide, prepared from potassium (9.5 g.) and *t*-butanol (200 ml), and dimethyl succinate (45 ml). The mixture was then stirred for further 2 hr. The reaction was then allowed to proceed for 12-14 hr. without stirring and worked up. The unchanged keto-ester (I: R=H; $R_1=Me$) was recovered (1 g.).

2-1'-Methoxycarbonyl ethyl-3-2'-methoxycarbonyl ethylindene (III: R = R_1 = Me).—
(a). The preceding crude acidic material (36 g.), obtained from the Stobbe condensation, was hydrolysed and decarboxylated according to the method of Sen *et al*'. The crude dibasic acid (25 g.) was esterified with a mixture of methanol (200 ml) and H_2SO_4 (conc., 25 ml) by refluxing for 48 hr. to afford the desired product (21 g.) as a very pale yellow viscous liquid; b. p. 170-75°/0.4 mm, λ_{max} 258 μ (ϵ , 12590). (Found: C, 70.61; H, 7.06. $C_{17}H_{20}O_4$ requires C, 70.81; H, 6.99%).

(b). When the above crude dibasic acid was esterified with ethereal diazomethane, the resulting dimethyl ester showed λ_{max} 259 μ (ϵ , 7413), b.p. 175-77°/0.4 mm. (Found: C, 70.48; H, 6.90. $C_{17}H_{20}O_4$ requires C, 70.81; H, 6.99 and $C_{16}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 70.06; H, 6.61%).

2-1'-Carboxyethyl-3-2'-carboxyethylindene (III: R = R_1 = H).—The dimethyl ester (III: R = R_1 = Me; 1 g.) was saponified with a mixture of NaOH (1 g.), water (1 ml), and methanol (10 ml) by refluxing for 4 hr. The pale yellow acidic material (900 mg.), m.p. 155-60°, was crystallised first from benzene ($\times 2$) and then from aqueous methanol ($\times 3$) to afford colorless plates, m.p. 163-64°, λ_{max} 262 μ (ϵ , 12500). (Found: C, 68.95; H, 6.15. $C_{15}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 69.23; H, 6.19%).

1-2'-Methoxycarbonyl ethyl-2-1'-methoxycarbonyl ethylindane (IV: R = R_1 = Me).—
(a). A solution of the dimethyl ester (III: R = R_1 = Me; 9 g.) in 95% ethanol (50 ml) was hydrogenated over 10% Pd/C (225 mg.). A portion of the saturated product (1 g.) was chromatographed over alumina (30 g.), using petroleum (60-80°). The middle fractions of the eluted material were collected and evaporatively distilled at 140-45°/0.4 mm to afford a colorless oil. (Found: C, 69.96; H, 8.05. $C_{17}H_{22}O_4$ requires C, 70.31; H, 7.64%).

(b). The dibasic acid (IV: $R_1=R$ = H) (1.3 g.), m.p. 168°, was esterified with ethereal diazomethane to afford the dimethyl ester (A, 1.3 g.) evaporatively distilling at 135°/0.1 mm. (Found: C, 70.37; H, 7.36. $C_{17}H_{22}O_4$ requires C, 70.31; H, 7.64%).

(c). In a similar manner the half-ester (IV: R = H; R₁ = Me) (1.5 g.), m.p. 113°, afforded the dimethyl ester (B, 1.1 g.), evaporatively distilling at 143°/0.2 mm. (Found: C, 70.30; H, 7.76. C₁₇H₂₂O₄ requires C, 70.31; H, 7.64%).

Equilibration of the Dimethyl Esters (IV: R = R₁ = Me; A and B).—(a). To a solution of sodium methoxide, prepared from sodium (1 g.) and magnesium-dried methanol (8.5 ml), was added a solution of the above dimethyl ester (A, 240 mg.) in methanol (1 ml) and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 1 hr. After addition of water (1.5 ml), the homogeneous solution was refluxed for 2 hr. On working up, the gummy acidic material (150 mg.) solidified slowly. One crystallisation from ether furnished crystals, m.p. 130-32° (melt turbid). The neutral substance contained ketonic material as indicated by the formation of a 2,4-DNP, m.p. 216°.

(b). A similar treatment of the above dimethyl ester (B, 300 mg.) afforded a mixture of dibasic acids (210 mg.), which was crystallised once from a mixture of ether and petroleum (60-80°), m. p. 135°. Here also, the neutral material furnished a 2,4-DNP, m. p. 215°.

The equilibration of the dimethyl ester (A, 300 mg.) with a solution of sodium methoxide, prepared from sodium (50 mg.) and magnesium-dried methanol (4 ml), by refluxing for 7 hr. was not very efficient because this procedure furnished a solid acidic material (265 mg.), which on trituration with a little ether furnished a material, melting at 167° and shrinking considerably at 164°. Fractional crystallisations of this material afforded the acid (8 mg.), m.p. 146.5°, shrinking at 135°. The neutral reaction product did not furnish any 2,4-DNP.

2-1'-Carboxyethyl-1-2'-methoxycarbonylethylindane (IV: R = H; R₁ = Me).—A solution of the preceding mixture of the unsaturated ester (III: R = R₁ = Me) and the lactonic material (4.5 g.) in 95% ethanol (35 ml) was hydrogenated over 10% Pd/C (250 mg.). The product, after removal of the solvent, was taken up in ether and washed thoroughly with aqueous sodium carbonate. The alkaline solution on acidification with HCl (cold, dilute) furnished the half-ester (1.43 g.), crystallising from a mixture of ether and petroleum (b.p. 40-60°), m.p. 113°. (Found: C, 69.82; H, 7.48; neut. equiv., 278. C₁₆H₂₀O₄ requires C, 69.55; H, 7.29%; neut. equiv., 276.32). The neutral material furnished the dimethyl ester (IV: R₁ = R = Me).

1-2'-Carboxyethyl-2-1'-methoxycarbonylethylindane (IV: R = Me; R₁ = H).—A homogeneous mixture of the dimethyl ester (IV: R = R₁ = Me; B, 265 mg.), methanol (0.5 ml), and an alkali solution (0.5 ml) (prepared from 560 mg. KOH, 0.5 ml. water, and methanol, 5.5 ml) was allowed to stand at the room temperature for 16 hr. On working up, the solid acidic residue (220 mg.) was crystallised from petroleum (40-60°) containing a little ether to afford crystals (180 mg.), m.p. 85-89°. Four recrystallisations from the same solvent furnished the pure material, m.p. 90.5-91.5°; when admixed with the isomeric half-ester, it melted at 77-79°. (Found: C, 69.41; H, 7.38. C₁₆H₂₀O₄ requires C, 69.55; H, 7.29%).

1-2'-Carboxyethyl-2-1'-carboxyethylindane (IV: R = R₁ = H).—(a). The half-ester (IV: R = H; R₁ = Me; 1.2 g.) was saponified with 10% methanolic KOH solution (4*M*) by refluxing for 4 hr. The acidic material (1.1 g.), m.p. 140-44°, was first triturated with a

little ether and then crystallised twice from a mixture of ether and petroleum (40-60°), m.p. 147.5°. (Found: C, 68.32; H, 7.09; neut. equiv., 132.6. $C_{15}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 68.71; H, 6.92%; neut. equiv., 131.15).

(b). The isomeric mixture of the saturated dimethyl ester (IV: R = R₁ = Me; 7 g.) was saponified in a similar manner and the crude dibasic acid (6.3 g.), m.p. 154°, shrinking at 127°, was triturated with ether and then crystallised repeatedly from dilute ethanol to furnish the pure acid (2.3 g.), m.p. 168.68-5°, admixture of which with the above acid melted at 137-38°. (Found: C, 69.02; H, 7.30; neut. equiv., 132. $C_{15}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 68.71; H, 6.92%; neut. equiv., 131.1).

From the above crystallisations and ethereal solution were obtained crystals (1.8 g.), m.p. 134°, which were dissolved in ether (10 ml) and kept in a frigidaire for several days. The resulting crystals were removed and the filtrate was concentrated (5 ml) and kept in cold when crystals (500 mg.), m.p. 145°, shrinking at 135°, were obtained. This material, on recrystallisations from a mixture of ether and petroleum (40-60°), afforded the pure isomeric dibasic acid (270 mg.), m.p. 146-47°.

(c). The unsaturated dibasic acid (III: R = R₁ = H; 500 mg.) was hydrogenated in glacial acetic acid (50 ml) over platinum oxide (50 mg.). The resulting material, m.p. 159-60°, was crystallised once from benzene, m.p. 164-65°; the latter on three recrystallisations from a mixture of methanol and benzene furnished the pure dibasic acid, m.p. 167-68°.

3-Methoxycarbonyl-1-methyl-2-oxo-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrofluorene (V).—To a mixture of the unsaturated dimethyl ester (III: R = R₁ = Me; 1 g.) in thiophene-free benzene (15 ml) and sodium hydride (130 mg.) was added, under nitrogen, one drop of methanol. It was refluxed for 2½ hr. The reaction mixture, on working up with cold very dilute hydrochloric acid and 2% sodium bicarbonate, afforded a dark brown gummy material (900 mg.), which on evaporative distillation at 120-25°/0.05 mm furnished a yellow viscous oil. The oil on treatment with a few drops of methanol and keeping in a frigidaire furnished a pale yellow solid, m.p. 72-73°; it was then crystallised once from methanol to furnish a colorless material (560 mg.), m.p. 79-81°. A portion of this substance, on repeated recrystallisations from a mixture of methanol and petroleum (40-60°), afforded the pure material, m.p. 83-84°, $\lambda_{\max}$ 249 μ (ϵ , 14960), which developed an intense violet colour with EtOH-FeCl₃. (Found: C, 74.98; H, 6.33. $C_{16}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 74.99; H, 6.29%).

When the Dieckmann reaction was carried out with sodium methoxide (2M) in benzene solution by heating for 4 hr., the yield of the desired product was 48.8%. With metallic sodium and a drop of methanol as catalyst, the yield was 50%.

1-Methyl-2-oxo-2,3,4,11-tetrahydrofluorene (VI).—A solution of the above β -keto-ester (500 mg.) in glacial acetic (25 ml) and 10% aqueous solution (5 ml) of H₂SO₄ was refluxed under nitrogen for 4 hr. Evolution of CO₂ was perceptible during first 2 hr. The light yellow solution was poured on a large volume of water having a top layer of ether. The acidic solution was basified with solid sodium carbonate. The product was worked up to furnish a pale yellow solid with adhering oil; it was subjected to short-path distillation at 90-100°/0.05mm to afford a colorless mixture of solid and liquid (320 mg.), showing a green ferric reaction. It was then chromatographed over alumina (15 g.) using petroleum (b.p. 40-80°) and then a mixture of the same solvent and benzene (9:1). First

few fractions (total, 60 mg) eluted with light petroleum showed positive ferric reaction. The rest of the fractions, having negative ferric reaction, were collected to afford a solid (250 mg.), m.p. 100-105°, which was crystallised thrice from a mixture of methanol and petroleum (60-80°) and once from methanol to provide a pure component (40 mg.), m.p. 126-27°, λ_{max} 251-252 m μ (ϵ , 9.374), $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{CHCl}_3}$ 1660 cm $^{-1}$ (broad). (Found: C, 84.82; H, 7.34. C $_{14}$ H $_{14}$ O requires C, 84.78; H, 7.15%.)

The residual liquor after crystallisations was evaporatively distilled at 85-90°/0.05 mm to furnish a material, m.p. 110-15°. (Found: C, 84.70; H, 7.29. C $_{14}$ H $_{14}$ O requires C, 84.81; H, 7.17%.)

The *semicarbazone* of the unsaturated ketone, m.p. 126-27°, was crystallised from a mixture of methanol and ethyl acetate in colorless plates, m.p. 220-21° (decomp.). (Found: N, 10.58. C $_{15}$ H $_{17}$ N $_3$ O requires N, 16.45%.)

The 2,4-*DNP*, prepared from the unsaturated ketone, m.p. 110-15°, was purified through chromatography and crystallisations from benzene and then from a mixture of methanol and ethyl acetate in red plates, m.p. 225-26° (decomp.). (Found: N, 15.21. C $_{20}$ H $_{18}$ O $_4$ N $_2$ requires N, 14.80%.)

1-Methylfluorene.—A mixture of the above crude gummy β -keto-ester (900 mg.), glacial acetic acid (2 ml), and 6*N*-HCl (10 ml) was refluxed under nitrogen for 4 hr. to afford a yellow material (350 mg.), m.p. 70-75°; it was subjected to short-path distillation at 95-100°/1.5-2 mm to furnish a colorless solid (250 mg.), m.p. 81-83°. Four crystallisations from a mixture of ether and petroleum (40-60°) furnished plates, m.p. 87°, λ_{max} 264 m μ (ϵ , 19800) (lit 14 , m.p. 85°). (Found: C, 93.13; H, 6.68. Calc. for C $_{14}$ H $_{14}$: C, 93.28; H, 6.71%.)

2-Hydroxy-3-methoxycarbonyl-1-methylfluorene (VII : R=CO $_2$ Me).—To a solution of the unsaturated β -keto-ester (500 mg.) in methanol (20 ml) was added HCl (conc., 2-3 drops) and the resulting solution was allowed to stand for 12-16 hr. at the room temperature (25-30°) when colorless long needles separated. These were filtered and washed with methanol. The combined filtrate and washings were concentrated, treated with 2-3 drops of HCl, and left for 3 days. It was diluted with water and the precipitated material was collected with ether to provide a crude product (150 mg.), which on crystallisation from methanol furnished the same material (50 mg.). The crystalline material (350 mg.), m.p. 139-40°, was chromatographed over alumina (12 g.), using petroleum(40-60°). The eluates furnished a material (340 mg.), m.p. 140-41°. Three crystallisations from methanol afforded needles (200 mg.), m.p. 143-44°, λ_{max} 247, 273, and 284 m μ (ϵ , 29010, 16210, and 13530 respectively). It showed a green ferric reaction. (Found: C, 75.55; H, 5.26. C $_{16}$ H $_{14}$ O $_3$ requires C, 75.58; H, 5.55%). This phenolic compound on treatment with ethereal diazomethane remained unchanged.

The yield of the above reaction decreased to a considerable extent when the reaction was carried out either in methanolic or acetic acid solution with a few drops of 10% H $_2$ SO $_4$ solution.

3-Carboxy-2-hydroxy-1-methylfluorene (VII : R=CO $_2$ H).—A mixture of the above phenolic ester (550 mg.), KOH (1 g.), and methanol (16 ml) was refluxed for 4 hr. when

a voluminous colorless solid separated within 5 min. The precipitate was filtered and washed with a little water. The potassium salt (500 mg.) was dissolved in water (250 ml) by heating, cooled, and acidified with HCl (conc.) to provide a pale yellow acidic material (450 mg.), m.p. 242-44° (decomp.). The filtrate and washings furnished the crude acidic material (50 mg.), m.p. 230-36°. Three crystallisations from a mixture of ether and benzene afforded very faint yellow needles (200 mg.), m.p. 245° (decomp.), $\lambda_{\max}$ 278-280 and 330 m μ (ϵ , 19680 and 14160 respectively); it developed a blue colour with EtOH-FeCl₃. (Found: C, 74.98; H, 5.31. C₁₃H₁₂O₃ requires C, 75.05; H, 5.03%). This acid on treatment with ethereal diazomethane furnished the phenolic ester (VII: R = CO₂Me) in 94.3% yield: m.p. 143-44°.

2-Hydroxy-1-methylfluorene (VII: R = H).—(a). A mixture of a solution of the ketone (VI, m.p. 115-20°) (400 mg.) in xylene (10 ml) and 30% Pd/C (150 mg.) was refluxed under nitrogen for 2 hr. The catalyst was filtered and the filtrate after concentration furnished crystals (300 mg.), m.p. 182-83.5°. Three recrystallisations from benzene afforded the pure product in needles (160 mg.), m.p. 184-85°, $\lambda_{\max}$ 274-275 m μ (ϵ , 20260). It did not respond to the ferric reaction. (Found: C, 85.35; H, 6.20. C₁₄H₁₂O requires C, 85.70; H, 6.16%).

(b). A mixture of the above phenolic acid (200 mg.), quinoline (4 ml), and copper bronze (100 mg.) was heated (bath temp. 220-30°) in an oil bath for 1 hr. and for another hour at 250-60° (bath temp.). On working up was obtained a residue (150 mg.), m.p. 178-80°, which on crystallisation from benzene afforded the pure material (100 mg.), m.p. 183-84°; the m.p. remained undepressed on admixture with a sample prepared under (a).

1,2,3,4,10,11-Hexahydro-3-methoxycarbonyl-1-methyl-2-oxofluorene (VIII: R=H; R₁=CO₂Me).—The unsaturated β -keto-ester (V) (2 g.) in 95% ethanol (125 ml) was hydrogenated over 5% Pd/C (400 mg.) when hydrogen (160 ml; calc. 190 ml) was absorbed in 2 hr. The product was triturated with a mixture of ethanol and ether (5 ml, 1:1) when a solid separated. This was washed with ethanol to furnish a colorless material (500 mg.), m.p. 112-14°; it was crystallised thrice from ether to afford small needles (150 mg.), m.p. 116-17°. It developed a violet colour with EtOH-FeCl₃. (Found: C, 74.56; H, 7.13. C₁₆H₁₈O₃ requires C, 74.39; H, 7.02%).

The volatile solvents from the filtrate and washings were removed and the residue was subjected to short-path distillation at 120-25°/0.2 mm to furnish a colorless mixture of oil and solid (1.2 g.), which showed a violet ferric reaction.

1,2,3,4,10,11-Hexahydro-1-methyl-2-oxofluorene (VIII: R = R₁ = H).—(a). An intimate mixture of the dibasic acid (IV: R = R₁ = H; A, 1 g., m.p. 167°) and lead carbonate (3 g.) was introduced, under nitrogen, into a preheated electrical chamber and the temperature was raised to and maintained at 295-310° for $\frac{1}{4}$ hr., when a yellow distillate was obtained. This ketonic material was subjected to short-path distillation to provide a colorless mixture of solid and liquid (550 mg.). The liquid portion (80 mg.) was pipetted and the residual solid was crystallised from light petroleum, m.p. 68.5°. (Found: C, 83.93; H, 7.74. C₁₄H₁₆O requires C, 83.95; H, 8.05%).

The *semicarbazone* was crystallised from methanol, m.p. 212-13° (decomp.). (Found: C, 69.89; H, 7.31; N, 16.37. C₁₃H₁₂ON₂ requires C, 70.04; H, 7.44; N, 16.33%).

The 2,4-DNP, m.p. 216.5° (decomp.), was crystallised from benzene in orange-yellow plates, m.p. 218° (decomp.). (Found: N, 14.55. $C_{20}H_{20}O_4N_4$ requires N, 14.72%).

The mixture of solid and oily ketonic material from the dibasic acid (m.p. 162°, shrinking at 132°) was chromatographed over alumina, using petroloum (60-80°), but there was no separation. The middle fraction of the chromatograph on short-path distillation at 90°/0.4mm provided the same mixture. (Found: C, 83.58; H, 8.32. $C_{14}H_{16}O$ requires C, 83.95; H, 8.05%).

The liquid portion of the above ketonic material, which did not furnish any crystalline ketone on keeping in a frigidaire, on short-path distillation furnished an almost colorless material. (Found: C, 83.51; H, 7.84. $C_{14}H_{16}O$ requires C, 83.95; H, 8.05%). This ketonic material was converted into its 2,4-DNP, which on fractional crystallisation from ethyl acetate yielded the above hydrazone, m.p. 218° (decomp.), and a small amount of a possibly non-homogeneous pale yellow derivative, m.p. 178-79° (decomp.). (Found: N, 14.85. $C_{20}H_{20}O_4N_4$ requires N, 14.72%).

Similar pyrolysis of the dibasic acid (IV: R = R₁ = H; B, m.p. 145.5°) yielded the same result.

(b). A mixture of the saturated dimethyl ester (IV: R = R₁ = Me; A, 1.05 g.), sodium (160 mg.), dry methanol (0.28 ml.) and thiophene-free benzene (10 ml) was refluxed under nitrogen for 8 hours to provide a gummy product (positive ferric reaction), which was refluxed with a mixture of 6*N*-HCl (10 ml) and glacial acetic acid (15 ml.). The reaction mixture was worked up and the product was purified to furnish the crystalline ketone with very little adhering oil in 38% yield.

Cyclisation and subsequent hydrolysis and decarboxylation of the saturated dimethyl ester (IV: R = R₁ = Me; B) afforded the same quality of ketone in 47% yield.

The hydrolysis and decarboxylation of the saturated crystalline β -keto-ester (VIII: R = H; R₁ = CO₂Me) afforded a ketonic material in 77.3% yield, which was converted into 2,4-DNP, m.p. 214-15° (decomp.), in 94% yield. From the saturated oily β -keto-ester (VIII: R = H; R₁ = CO₂Me) was obtained in 60% yield a ketonic material, which furnished the higher melting derivative in 54% yield.

(c). A solution of the unsaturated ketone (VI, 400 mg., m.p. 126-27°) in 95% ethanol (40 ml) was hydrogenated over 5% Pd/C (50 mg.). The calculated amount of hydrogen (50 ml) was absorbed in about 1 hr. The hydrogenated product was worked up and purified to provide a colorless mixture of solid and oil (360 mg.), a portion of which was converted into 2,4-DNP, m.p. 196-97° (decomp.) in 92% yield. On fractional crystallisation it furnished the higher melting product in 26% yield and the lower melting one in 13% yield.

(d). To a stirred blue solution of lithium (70 mg.) in liquid ammonia (200 ml) was added during 10-15 min. a solution of the unsaturated ketone (VI, 500 mg.) in dry ether (50 ml). The homogeneous blue solution was stirred for further 25-30 min. and then the colour was discharged with ammonium chloride (500-600 mg.). The reduction product was worked up and purified to provide a ketonic material (450 mg.), a portion of which was converted into 2,4-DNP, m.p. 215-16°, in 67% yield.

3-*Formyl-1,2,3,4,10,11-hexahydro-1-methyl-2-oxofluorene* (VIII: R = H; R₁ = CHO).—To a suspension of sodium methoxide, prepared from sodium (215 mg.) and magnesium-dried methanol (0.376 ml), in dry thiophene-free benzene (6.3 ml), cooled in ice, was added dropwise with shaking a solution of a mixture of ketone (VIII: R = R₁ = H; 750 mg., m.p. 66-67°) and freshly distilled ethyl formate (0.9 ml) in dry thiophene-free benzene (8 ml) during $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. Occasional shaking was continued for further 2 hr. and the reaction was allowed to proceed at the room temperature (27°) for 48 hr. It was worked up successively with ice, 2% NaOH solution, 3*N*-HCl, and ether to furnish a yellow solid (870 mg.), which developed an intense violet colour with EtOH-FeCl₃. A portion of this crude formyl compound was crystallised from petroleum (40-60°) in colorless crystals, m.p. 82-83°. It was sublimed at 80°/0.05 mm to furnish a sublimate, melting at 83-84°. (Found: C, 78.72; H, 7.54. C₁₅H₁₆O₂ requires C, 78.94; H, 7.07%.)

The oily ketone (VIII: R = R₁ = H; 1.5 g.) on similar formylation furnished the crude formyl compound (1.6 g.), m.p. 79°.

3-*Anilinomethylene-1,2,3,4,10,11-hexahydro-1-methyl-2-oxofluorene* (IX).—A solution of the crude formyl derivative (7.05 g.) in dry thiophene-free benzene (10 ml) was distilled (5.5 ml). The residual solution, cooled to the room temperature (27°), was treated with dry methanol (55 ml), followed by monomethylaniline (10.5 ml), and left at the room temperature (27°) for 16 hr. It was then cooled in ice when yellow crystals separated (when a gummy material separated, a part of it was evaporatively distilled at 170°/0.05 mm to provide viscous distillate, which on scratching with a little solvent furnished crystals, on seeding, the whole oily material solidified). The crystals were filtered and washed with petroleum (60-80°); yield 5.2 g., m.p. 113-14° (crude).

To the combined filtrate and washings was added dry thiophene-free benzene (10 ml) and the solvent was slowly distilled. Fresh solvent (75 ml $\times$ 2) was added and the distillation continued till it stopped. Finally it was heated at 85-95°/2.5 mm for 1 hr. The residual dark brown material solidified on treatment with ether. It was crystallised from ether to furnish a yellow material (1.4 g.), m.p. 117-19°. A portion of the product was crystallised from a mixture of ether and petroleum (b.p. 40-60°), m.p. 119.5-20°. (Found: C, 83.60; H, 7.47; N, 4.35. C₂₂H₂₃ON requires C, 83.22; H, 7.30; N, 4.41%.)

The residue, obtained from the mother liquors of crystallisations, on successive treatment with 10% HCl (aq.) and 8% KOH (aq.), afforded the original ketone (1.1 g.).

1-2'-*Carboxyethyl-1,2,3,4,10,11-hexahydro-1-methyl-2-oxofluorene* (VIII: R = CH₂-CH₂-CO₂H; R₁ = H).—To a solution of the above anilinomethylene compound (1.5 g., m.p. 117-19°) in a mixture of dry thiophene-free benzene (35 ml) and *t*-butanol (70 ml) was added under nitrogen freshly distilled acrylonitrile (930 mg.), followed by a solution of dry Triton-B (from 3.5 ml of 35% methanolic solution) in *t*-butanol (25 ml) and water (0.25 ml). The reaction was allowed to proceed at the room temperature (28°) for 14 hr. and at 55° for 30 hr. After removal of the volatile material, the residue was worked up with ether to furnish a golden yellow solid (2 g.), which was refluxed under nitrogen with a solution of KOH (2.8 g.) in water (17.5 ml) for 6 hr. to afford a solid (720 mg.), m.p. 126°. This crude product on short-path distillation at 160-65°/0.3 mm furnished a colorless distillate (600 mg.), m.p. 135-38°. Two crystallisations from ether afforded the pure material, m.p. 136-39°. (Found: Neut. equiv., 269. C₁₇H₂₃O₃ requires neut. equiv., 272). It was recrystallised twice

from the same solvent to afford the pure material (10 mg.), m. p. 139-40° (possibly not homogeneous). (Found: C, 74.91; H, 7.48. $C_{17}H_{20}O_2$ requires C, 74.98; H, 7.40%).

Enol Lactone of 1-2'-Carboxyethyl-1, 2, 3, 4, 10, 11-hexahydro-1-methyl-2-oxofluorene (X).—A mixture of the crude keto-acid (VIII: $R = CH_2CH_2.CO_2H$; $R_1 = H$; 4.2 g.), freshly distilled acetic anhydride (45 ml) and anhydrous sodium acetate (30 mg.) was refluxed under nitrogen for 4 hr. in an oil bath (bath temp. 150°). The volatile material was removed and the residue was worked up with ether and aqueous sodium carbonate. The neutral material (3.8 g.), m. p. 109-10°, on short-path distillation at 130°/0.15 mm furnished a colorless product (2.5 g.), which was crystallised from ether; yield 2 g., m. p. 108-15°. Two more recrystallisations afforded needles, m. p. 110-16.5°. (Found: C, 80.30; H, 7.20. $C_{17}H_{18}O_2$ requires C, 80.30; H, 7.13%).

The aqueous alkaline solution provided the original keto-acid (40 mg.) and the residue in the sublimation tube, on alkali treatment, also furnished the keto-acid (300 mg.).

1, 2, 3, 4, 10, 11-Hexahydro-1-methyl-1-3'-oxobutyl-2-oxofluorene (VIII: $R = CH_2CH_2.CO_2Me$; $R_1 = H$).—To a solution of the enol lactone (800 mg., m. p. 108-15°) in a mixture of dry benzene (15 ml) and ether (15 ml.), cooled in ice, was added under nitrogen with constant stirring an ethereal solution of methylmagnesium iodide (40 % excess) during 15 min. Stirring was continued for another hour and the reaction mixture was worked up to provide a product (800 mg.) melting at 154-59°. It was washed with hot petroleum (60-80°) and repeatedly crystallised from a mixture of methanol and benzene in colorless crystals (100 mg.), m. p. 159-60°. (Found: C, 79.65; H, 8.07. $C_{18}H_{22}O_2$ requires C, 79.97; H, 8.20%).

1, 1a, 2, 3, 5, 6-Hexahydro-1a-methyl-3-oxochrysofluorene (XI).—To a stirred solution of sodium methoxide, prepared from sodium (280 mg.) and dry methanol (6.8 ml), cooled in ice, was added rapidly under nitrogen a solution of the unsaturated ketone (VI, 2 g.) in dry thiophene-free benzene (6 ml). To the resulting deep red solution was added during 30 min. with stirring and cooling a solution of the crystalline methiodide, prepared from 1-diethylaminobutan-3-one (1.23 g.) and methyl iodide (0.51 ml), in a mixture of dry thiophene-free benzene (6 ml) and methanol (2 ml). Stirring was continued in the cold for further 3½ hr. and then the reaction mixture was refluxed for 1 hr. On working up, it furnished a dark brown gummy product (2 g.), which was triturated with ether (5 ml × 2) to furnish a pale yellow solid (900 mg.), m. p. 133-35°. A solution of this in a mixture of petroleum (60-80°) and benzene (1 : 1, 20 ml) was poured on a column of alumina (21 g. in light petroleum) and eluted first with light petroleum and then with a mixture of light petroleum and benzene (9:1) to afford crystals (800 mg.), m. p. 137-39°. The material (1.3 g.), obtained on evaporation of the solvent from the above ethereal solution, on similar purification, furnished the unsaturated ketone (XI, 330 mg.), m. p. 132-35°.

The combined product was recrystallised twice from ether to furnish a pale yellow material (700 mg.), m. p. 138-39°. Two more recrystallisations from the same solvent afforded colorless crystals, m. p. 140-41°; λ_{max} 226, 241, 251, and 257 m μ (ϵ , 18250, 18260, 18200, and 16600 respectively). (Found: C, 86.18; H, 7.48. $C_{18}H_{18}O$ requires C, 86.36; H, 7.24%).

The *semicarbazone* was crystallised from ethanol, m. p. 252-53° (decomp.). (Found: N, 13.61. $C_{18}H_{18}ON_3$ requires N, 13.66%).

The 2, 4-*DNP* was first crystallised from benzene and then from a mixture of benzene-ethyl acetate-ethanol to afford red plates, m.p. 240-41° (decomp.). (Found: N, 13.38. $C_{24}H_{22}O_4N_4$ requires N, 13.00%).

Chrysofluorene.—(a). To a mixture of $LiAlH_4$ (300 mg.) and dry ether (100 ml) was added a solution of the unsaturated ketone (XI, 500 mg.) in dry thiophene-free benzene (10 ml) and the mixture was refluxed for 20 min. The product on short-path distillation at 145-50°/0.05 mm furnished a glassy material (400 mg.), which was dehydrogenated with 30% Pd/C (500 mg.) to afford the hydrocarbon (300 mg.). It was crystallised once from a mixture of benzene and methanol and then chromatographed to furnish crystals (150 mg.), m.p. 181-83°, which was recrystallised twice from a mixture of the same solvents, once from methanol and then sublimed at 100-10°/0.4 mm to afford a colorless material, m.p. 186° (lit.²³, m.p. 188°). (Found: C, 94.32; H, 5.61. Calc. for $C_{17}H_{12}$: C, 94.43; H, 5.59%).

(b). Similar reduction and dehydrogenation of the unsaturated ketone (XIV, m.p. 94°, shrinking at 88°) afforded the hydrocarbon, m.p. 185-87°, the mixed m.p. of which with the above sample remained undepressed.

11-*Oxochrysofluorene*.—The preceding hydrocarbon (40 mg.) was refluxed with a solution of sodium dichromate dihydrate (100 mg.) in glacial acetic acid (3 ml) for 20 min., when the reaction mixture assumed a green colour. On working up, followed by chromatography, an orange product (35 mg.) was obtained, m.p. 132°. Three crystallisations from petroleum (60-80°) afforded the pure orange material, m.p. 134° (lit.²³ m.p. 135°). (Found: C, 88.58; H, 4.65. Calc. for $C_{17}H_{10}O$: C, 88.67; H, 4.37%).

3-*Ethylenedioxy-1, 1a, 2, 3, 4, 6-hexahydro-1a-methylchrysofluorene* (XII).—A mixture of the unsaturated ketone (XI, 1.5 g.), dry toluene (90 ml), ethylene glycol (16 ml), and *p*-toluenesulphonic acid monohydrate (70 mg.) was distilled very slowly, fresh toluene being replenished at frequent intervals. The distillate (125 ml) was collected during 6 hr. and the residue was worked up to provide a pale yellow crystalline material (1.5 g.), m.p. 112-14°. Three recrystallisations from petroleum (40-80°), followed by two more from methanol, afforded a pale yellow material, m.p. 120-21°, λ_{max} 258-259 $m\mu$ (ϵ , 11810). (Found: C, 81.45; H, 7.37. $C_{20}H_{22}O_2$ requires C, 81.59; H, 7.53%). Chromatography did not remove the colour.

3-*Ethylenedioxy-1a-methyl-1, 1a, 1b, 2, 3, 4, 6, 6a-octahydrochrysofluorene* (XIII).—(a). To a stirred homogeneous mixture of liquid ammonia (300 ml) and a solution of the ketal (1 g.) in dry ether (125 ml) was added rapidly lithium (1.2 g.). The resulting blue solution was stirred for 45 min. and then the colour was discharged with dry ethanol (12 ml). The resulting yellow reduction product (1 g.) was triturated with methanol (3 ml $\times$ 2) to furnish a solid (250 mg.), which was crystallised thrice from methanol to provide the colorless pure ketal (A, 25 mg.), m.p. 123°, λ_{max} 265-266 $m\mu$ (ϵ , 739). (Found: C, 80.96; H, 8.29. $C_{20}H_{24}O_2$ requires C, 81.04; H, 8.16%). This substance on admixture with the original ketal (XII) melted at 103-105°.

(b). The reduced ketal (1.5 g.), obtained on similar reduction of the ketal (XII, 1.5 g.), was chromatographed over alumina (60 g.) using petroleum (60-80°) and then a mixture

of petroleum-benzene (9:1) as the eluents (50-60 ml in each fraction). Fraction III (b.p. 60-80; 240 mg.) was rechromatographed to furnish the ketal (A, 30 mg.). Fraction IV (290 mg.) was crystallised from methanol to provide the ketal (A, 20 mg.).

Fractions V-VI (480 mg.) were crystallised from the same solvent to afford ketal (A, 70 mg.). The oily residue (390 mg.), obtained from the mother liquors of these crystallisations, was rechromatographed on alumina (23 g.) and the resulting mixture of crystals and oils (200 mg.) was repeatedly crystallised to furnish the pure product (A, 10 mg.). The mother liquors of the latter crystallisations were combined and concentrated to furnish crystals (90 mg.), m.p. 123-25°, which were recrystallised twice from methanol to afford the pure material (B, 40 mg.), m.p., 125-26°, $\lambda_{\max}$ 266 m μ (ϵ , 1894). (Found: C, 81.32; H, 8.16. $C_{20}H_{24}O_2$ requires C, 81.04; H, 8.16%). This substance on admixture with (A) melted at 114-16°. The remaining fractions (VIII-XV, 250 mg.), on similar crystallisations and chromatography, afforded ketals (A, 80 mg.) and (B, 10 mg.).

(c). When the metal-ammonia reduction of the ketal (XII, 800 mg.) was carried out with lithium (80 mg.), the yield of the higher-melting ketal (B) was 10%.

1a-Methyl-1.1a.1b.2.3.5.6,6a-octahydro-3-oxochrysofluorene (XIV).—(a). A mixture of the ketal (XIII: A, 370 mg., m.p. 120-22°), dry acetone (20 ml), and *p*-toluenesulphonic acid monohydrate (30 mg.) was refluxed for 4 hr. The solution was concentrated (5 ml) and water was added dropwise to the point of incipient cloudiness. The crystalline product (320 mg.), m.p. 97-99°, on repeated recrystallisations from petroleum (b.p. 40-60°) afforded the pure material, m.p. 102-103°, $\lambda_{\max}$ 236-239 m μ (ϵ , 19530). (Found: C, 85.67; H, 8.35. $C_{18}H_{20}O$ requires C, 85.70; H, 7.99%).

The 2,4-DNP was crystallised from a mixture of benzene and methanol, m.p. 245° (decomp.). (Found: N, 12.99. $C_{12}H_{16}O_4N_4$ requires N, 12.96%).

(b). The ketal (XIII: B, 30 mg., m.p. 125-26°) on similar treatment⁴ furnished a product (24 mg.), which on recrystallisations from petroleum (60-80°) provided the pure product, m.p. 143-44°, $\lambda_{\max}$ 236-239 m μ (ϵ , 15490). (Found: C, 85.69; H, 7.99. $C_{18}H_{20}O$ requires C, 85.70; H, 7.99%).

The 2,4-DNP was crystallised from benzene, m.p. 255-56° (decomp.). (Found: N, 13.38. $C_{12}H_{16}O_4N_4$ requires N, 12.96%). This material on admixture with the above 2,4-DNP melted at 220-25° (decomp.).

(c). The diketone (VIII: R=CH₂CH₂COMe; R₁=H; m.p. 160°, shrinking at 153°; 250 mg.) was refluxed under nitrogen with a solution of NaOH (250 mg.) in a mixture of water (1 ml) and methanol (24 ml) to furnish a product (205 mg.), which was evaporatively distilled at 115°/0.3 mm to provide a colorless material (160 mg.), m.p. 94°, shrinking at 88°. Two crystallisations from light petroleum, followed by distillation, afforded the pure material (100 mg.), m.p. 95°, shrinking at 90°; $\lambda_{\max}$ 237 and 241 m μ (ϵ , 12590 and 12500 respectively). (Found: C, 85.62; H, 8.03. $C_{18}H_{20}O$ requires C, 85.70; H, 7.99%). Chromatography did not improve the m.p.

1, 1a, 1b, 2, 3, 4, 4a, 5, 6, 6a-Decahydro-1a-methyl-3-oxochrysofluorene (XV).—(a). A solution of the ketone (XI, 500 mg.) in 95% ethanol (100 ml) was hydrogenated over 5%

Pd/C (100 mg.). The calculated amount of hydrogen (112 ml) was absorbed in about 1½ hr. to provide an oily product, which was subjected to short-path distillation at 135-40°/0.2mm to furnish a thick oil (400 mg.). The distillate was dissolved in benzene (3ml) and poured on alumina (20 g.) and eluted. The oily and solid materials (310 mg.), eluted with petroleum (60-80°) and a mixture of petroleum and benzene (9:1), was crystallised from methanol, m.p. 129-31°, yield 70 mg. On recrystallisations from methanol, it afforded the pure substance, m.p. 132-33°, λ_{max} 206 μ (ϵ , 1034). (Found: C, 84.92; H, 8.77. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}$ requires C, 84.99; H, 8.72%).

The *semicarbazone* was crystallised thrice from ethanol, m.p. 220-21° (decomp.). (Found: N, 13.50. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{12}\text{ON}_3$ requires N, 13.48%).

A similar reduction of the ketone (XI) in presence of a little aqueous KOH did not change the rate of absorption.

(b). The ketone (XIV, 250 mg., m.p. 94°, shrinking at 88°), prepared as in (c) in 95% ethanol, was hydrogenated over 10% Pd/C (70 mg.); the absorption of hydrogen stopped within 10 min. The hydrogenated product was repeatedly chromatographed and crystallised to afford the ketone (60 mg.), m.p. 132-33°, remaining undepressed on admixture with the above sample.

3-Acetoxy-1. Ia, Ib, 2, 3, 4, 4a, 5, 6, 6a-decahydro-1a-methylchrysofluorene.—The oily ketone (XV, 900 mg.), obtained after removal of the crystalline ketone, was treated with LiAlH_4 (600 mg.) in dry ether (100 ml) to furnish a thick alcohol, which was acetylated with acetic anhydride (2.5 ml) and pyridine (5 ml). The resulting pale yellow acetate was evaporatively distilled at 140-45°/0.05mm, providing a colorless glassy distillate (800 mg.). Similar redistillations furnished the analytical sample (glassy). (Found: C, 80.06; H, 8.53. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 80.49; H, 8.78%).

(?)-Bromo-1, Ia, Ib, 2, 3, 4, 4a, 5, 6, 6a-decahydro-1a-methyl-3-oxochrysofluorene.—To a solution of the ketone (XV, 100 mg., m.p. 132-33°) in glacial acetic acid (3 ml) containing one drop of 48% hydrobromic acid, cooled in ice, was added a solution of bromine in acetic acid (3.2 ml, equivalent to 630 mg. of bromine) over a period of ¼ hr. The reaction was then allowed to stand for 1 hr., when a crop of crystals separated. The crystalline material was filtered and recrystallised from ether, m.p. 185° (decomp.). (Found: C, 64.79; H, 6.38. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{21}\text{OBr}$ requires C, 64.85; H, 6.35%).

The authors' grateful thanks are due to Professor Dr. D. K. Banerjee, F. A. Sc., F. N. I., for his keen interest in this work, to East India Pharmaceutical Works Ltd., and the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi, for the awards of a scholarship (A.K.B.) and a senior research fellowship (B. P. S.), respectively.